

FEM ANALYSIS ON OUT-OF-PLANE THERMAL EXPANSION IN PLAIN WEAVE COMPOSITE

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1. Introduction

Composites have been increasingly recognized as important materials in aerospace structures. However, the compression after impact (CAI) strength of composites is relatively poor that it may prohibit their application as upper skin panels. To improve CAI strength, plain weave composites have been proposed and studied. Naik and Ganesh suggested the elemental array model that can present a precise geometry and investigated thermo-mechanical properties and fracture strength [1-2]. Tanaka and Watanabe have developed FEM analysis of CF/Epoxy plain weave composite including thermal effects using 3-D FEM and the homogenization method [3]. In these studies, they also investigated thermal behavior of plain weave composite. However, these studies focused only in-plane behaviors and there are a few reports about out-of-plane coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE). On the other hand, Dasgupta et al. investigated thermal property of E-glass/Epoxy plain weave composite [3] and showed the value of α_z became three times higher than that of in-plane directions. The CTE is important factor of aerospace fields because of their hard temperature environment. The purpose of this study is to confirm the out-of-plane CTE of CF/Epoxy plain weave composite mainly by FEM analysis.

2. Experiments

2.1 Test Specimen

Plain weave specimen was made of T-300 carbon fiber and XNR/H 6813 resin with the method of vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VaRTM) where the curing temperature was 120°C. Table 1 shows the mechanical and thermal properties of fiber and epoxy resin. The stacking sequence was [0/90]₃₁.

Three specimens were prepared, each having dimension of 5×5×10.5 mm. Fiber volume fraction V_f of these specimens was about 51.6%.

Table 1 Mechanical and thermal property

	E_L [GPa]	E_T [GPa]	α_L [K ⁻¹]	α_T [K ⁻¹]
Fiber	230	40	-0.4×10^{-6}	26×10^{-6}
Epoxy		2.8		68×10^{-6}

2.2 Apparatus and Procedures

As for the machine which measured thermal expansion, DIL 402C made by NETZCH was used in this test. Increase rate and range of temperature are 3K/min and between 0 and 80 °C, respectively. The steps of test were as follows. Firstly, the specimen was put into a vacuum chamber together with a push rod carefully placed in contact with the specimen. Then, temperature within the chamber was gradually increased, and thermal expansion of specimen was measured by the displacement of the push rod, while the environmental temperature was measured simultaneously. CTE of each specimen was measured three times, and averaged values were obtained.

2.3 Results

Table 2 shows results together with the average and standard deviation.

Table 2 CTE of plain weave [$\times 10^{-6}$ K⁻¹]

	Measurement			Average	Standard Dev.
	1	2	3		
Sample 1	64.6	63.9	63.3	63.9	0.5
Sample 2	66.7	65.7	66.0	66.1	0.4
Sample 3	65.6	65.3	64.4	65.1	0.5
Total	-	-	-	65.1	-

Because the standard deviation is less than 1% of each average, the results have good accuracy. The average value from three specimens is $65.1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ of which value is very close to the CTE of epoxy in Table 1, the difference is less than 5%.

3. Analysis

3.1 Homogenization Method

The homogenization method is a rigorous analytical method to system composed of a large amount of periodic microstructures, which is microscopically heterogeneous. In the thermal-elasticity problem such as composite materials, this method gives considerably accurate distributions for highly and locally changing stresses in the small base cell that is a minimum unit. The deformation and the distribution of the thermal residual stresses after the curing process cannot be obtained accurately by the usual FEM because of the difficulty to define the exact boundary condition to woven composites without using the homogenization method [4].

The displacement $u_i^l(x, y)$ in micro levels are expressed as follows

$$u_i^l(x, y) = -\chi_i^{kl}(x, y) \frac{\partial u_k^0(x)}{\partial x_l} - \psi_i(x, y) \Delta T \quad (1)$$

where x and y are macroscopic and microscopic coordinate, $u_k^0(x)$ is macroscopic displacement, ΔT is temperature difference, χ_i^{kl} is characteristic displacement vector relating to a “ kl ” deformation mode of the base cell, and ψ_i is characteristic displacement resulting from the thermal deformation. Homogenized elastic constant E_{ijkl}^0 and thermo elastic constant A_{ijkl}^0 are obtained as follows

$$E_{ijkl}^0 = \frac{1}{|Y|} \int_{\mathbb{Y}} \left(E_{ijkl} - E_{ijpm} \frac{\partial \chi_p^{kl}}{\partial y_m} \right) dY \quad (2)$$

$$A_{ij}^0 = \frac{1}{|Y|} \left(E_{ijkl} \alpha_{kl} - E_{ijpm} \frac{\partial \psi_p}{\partial y_m} \right) dY \quad (3)$$

where $|Y|$ is volume of base cell, E_{ijkl} is elastic constant of constituents (fiber or matrix), and α_{kl} is coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) of

constituents. Homogenized CTE α_{ij}^0 is determined by the following equation

$$\alpha_{ij}^0 = E_{ijkl}^{-1} A_{kl}^0 \quad (4)$$

Thermal residual stress σ_{ij}^0 , which includes both the influence of microscopic and macroscopic structure, is determined by the following equation

$$\sigma_{ij}^0(x, y) = \left(E_{ijkl}(x, y) - E_{ijpm}(x, y) \frac{\partial \chi_p^{kl}}{\partial y_m} \right) \frac{\partial u_k^0(x)}{\partial x_l} - E_{ijkl}(x, y) \frac{\partial \psi_k(x, y)}{\partial y_l} - E_{ijkl}(x, y) \alpha_{kl} \Delta T \quad (5)$$

3.2 Analytical Model

The undulation of base cell was based on “elemental array model” [1-2]. Our FEM model is shown in Fig.1. Pink and green color regions indicate x- and y- fiber tow, and white region is pure epoxy. The constituent material and V_f is the same as specimen. Twenty nodes isoparametric elements are adopted. To adjust the same V_f as the test specimen, the phase difference between upper and lower layer of this model is shifted with quarter period both x- and y-direction.

Fig.1. Analytical model

3.3 Analytical Results

The CTE were obtained as follows

$$\alpha_z = 72.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$$

The analytical result shows that the out-of-plane CTE is very close to the CTE of epoxy in Table 1. The difference is less than 6%. It means that the out-of-plane CTE has the same tendency as experimental result. The difference between experiment and

analysis is only 10%. It means the accuracy of analysis is confirmed.

3.4 Effect of Thermal Residual Stress

Figure 2 indicates thermal residual stress distributions in the region as shown in Fig.1.

The residual stress σ_x in x-fiber tow is compressive because α_x is a negative value. On the other hand, the value in other constituents is tensile since their CTE in x-direction are positive. In the area near Point A in Fig.2, the value of σ_x is the weakest because the fiber content in z-direction is high. And it becomes high as the position becomes far from there. The value of σ_z is highly compressive in the Point B. And it becomes small and changes to tensile as the position shifts near to Point C.

(a) Stress distribution of σ_x

(b) Stress distribution of σ_z

Fig.2 Thermal residual stress distribution

To investigate the influence of thermal residual stresses on CTE, the sampling lines are taken in the analytical model along through-thickness direction. The position of each line is drawn in Fig. 3. Along Line 1, σ_z has the highest compressive stress, while it has the highest tensile stress along Line 2.

Fig.3 Position of sampling line

Table 3 and 4 show the z-displacement value in various constituent materials, namely epoxy, y-fiber tow and x-fiber tow, as well as the respective causes of the z-displacements. λ_{σ_z} is z-displacement due to out-of-plane thermal residual stress, λ_{σ_x} and λ_{σ_y} are values due to Poisson's effect of in-plane stresses, $\lambda_{\tau_{xz}}$ is value due to shearing stress caused by the influence of inclination of both fiber tows.

Table 3 Displacement along Line 1

	Epoxy [$\times 10^{-6}$ mm]	x-fiber tow [$\times 10^{-6}$ mm]	y-fiber tow [$\times 10^{-6}$ mm]	Total [$\times 10^{-6}$ mm]
λ_{σ_z}	-180.7	-557.6	-622.4	-1360.7
λ_{σ_x}	-64.5	-88.8	-92.1	-245.4
λ_{σ_y}	-79.7	45.2	-239.8	-274.3
$\lambda_{\tau_{xz}}$	-80.7	-199.2	12.6	-267.3
$\lambda_{\tau_{yz}}$	0	46.8	3.4	50.2
Total λ	-405.7	-938.3	-753.6	-2097.6

Table 4 Displacement along Line 2

	Epoxy [$\times 10^{-6}$ mm]	x-fiber tow [$\times 10^{-6}$ mm]	y-fiber tow [$\times 10^{-6}$ mm]	Total [$\times 10^{-6}$ mm]
λ_{σ_z}	-544	-468.5	-468.5	-1481.0
λ_{σ_x}	239.7	108.1	108.6	456.5
λ_{σ_y}	-324.6	12.6	-189.9	-501.9
$\lambda_{\tau_{xz}}$	-316.1	-192.8	10.3	-498.7
Total λ	-944.9	-540.8	-539.4	-2025.1

Along Line 1, the amount of displacement due to the thermal residual stresses, i.e. the sum of λ_{σ_x} , λ_{σ_y} and λ_{σ_z} accounts for 35% of total displacement. On the other hand, along Line 2, where the matrix content is the highest, because the strong tensile stress works in-plane directions and σ_z is tensile in Figure 2, the amount of λ_{σ_x} and λ_{σ_y} is 50% of the total displacement and λ_{σ_z} decreases the total by 23%. Therefore, the amount due to thermal residual stress becomes 27% of total displacement. These results demonstrate that one of main reasons why α_z in plain weave composite is larger than that of UD composite is the thermal residual stresses generated by complex weaving configuration.

3.5 Reason of 10% Difference

There is 10% difference between analytical and experimental results, and the reason is considered to be two kinds of difference between analysis and experiment: boundary condition and shape difference. Because the specimen is very small in in-plane direction, each surface is subjected to free stress condition and periodic boundary condition is not available. And because the analytical model has idealized shape to apply the homogenization method, there is shape difference between specimen and analytical model especially phase difference between layers.

To examine the influence of shape difference, three kinds of simple analytical models were considered; Model A is an idealized model which there is no shift between layers, Model B is shifted Model A with half period in x-direction and Model C is shifted with quarter period in both x- and y-directions as shown in Fig.4. Pink and green color regions indicate x- and y- fiber tow. Analytical method is the homogenization method and the material property is same as experiment. The values of α_z in these models were obtained as follows

$$\alpha_z = 77.2 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1} \text{ in Model A}$$

$$\alpha_z = 77.2 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1} \text{ in Model B}$$

$$\alpha_z = 84.4 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1} \text{ in Model C}$$

The α_z of Model C is 8.6% larger than other two models, and that of Model A and Model B becomes same value.

It is seemed that the difference is caused by elastic constant E_z of each model. These are as follows

$$E_z = 8.22 \text{ GPa in Model A}$$

$$E_z = 8.23 \text{ GPa in Model B}$$

$$E_z = 6.39 \text{ GPa in Model C}$$

The E_z of Model C is the smallest among several calculated models. Because the phase difference of analytical model for experiment is quarter period in both x- and y-directions same as Model C, it is confirmed that the shape difference affects 8.6% of out of plane CTE, and the reason of this effect is the difference of elastic constant of each model.

Fig.4 Simple analytical model

To clarify the effect of boundary condition, usual 3-D FEM analysis with free boundary condition is executed. The analysis was performed by the model which is based on Model A. the material property was same as before analysis.

Due to the requirement of computer, we cannot analyze 31ply model. Therefore, we compared the

value of 3-D FEM analysis of 30plys and 32plys that was obtained by symmetry condition of the z axis and the value of homogenization method. Figure 5 shows the 3-D FEM analytical model of 30plys. The 32plys model was made by the same method and adding more one layer.

Fig.5 3-D FEM analytical model of 30plys

The α_z of each model was obtained as follows

$$\alpha_z = 75.8 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1} \text{ in 30plys}$$

$$\alpha_z = 75.6 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1} \text{ in 32plys}$$

The α_z of 30plys and 32plys are about 2% smaller than the value of homogenization method. It is considered that the reason of this difference is generated by the thermal residual stress.

Figure 6 shows the thermal residual stress distribution σ_z and σ_x in 30plys model.

To observe the insight, the model was cut by two regions as shown in Fig.5: Region 2 shows σ_z distribution, and Region 3 shows σ_x . The thermal residual stress distribution of 32plys model also shows same tendency.

(a) Stress distribution of σ_z

(b) Stress distribution of σ_x

Fig.6 Thermal residual stress distribution in 30plys

Both of the thermal residual stress distribution becomes same tendency of homogenization method. However, because each side applied the free boundary condition, σ_z and σ_x become small as it approaches each boundary. The thermal residual stress accounts for about 25% of total deformation as mentioned in Section 3.4, and it is considered that the deformation of thermal residual stress become small if the values of residual stress become small. Therefore, it is confirmed that the difference of boundary condition decrease about 2% of out of plane CTE, and the reason of this result is caused by the decrease in thermal residual stress.

The total effect of shape difference and difference of boundary condition becomes 10.6%. Because this difference was corresponding to the difference of the experimental and analytical results, therefore, it was confirmed that these two differences were factors of the difference of experimental and analytical result.

4. Conclusion

Several conclusions can be drawn by analytical and experimental results of this study:

- 1) The experimental results with good accuracy which is $65.1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ are obtained.
- 2) The analytical result which was performed by homogenization method is $72.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$.
- 3) Because the difference between experiment and analysis is only 10%, the accuracy of analysis is confirmed.
- 4) The thermal residual stress accounts for about 25% of total deformation, it is confirmed the influence of complex thermal residual stress generated by complex weaving configuration.
- 5) It is considered that the reason of difference between experimental and analytical result is two factors: boundary condition and shape difference.
- 6) By farther analysis, it is confirmed that the differences of boundary condition and shape difference decrease 10.6% of out of plane CTE when compared with homogenization method. Because this value is corresponding to the difference of experimental and analytical result,

it is confirmed that the reason of difference between experiment and analysis.

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